

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The role of people management in public network hospitals in Brazil

Gomes Rickardo ^{1,*} and Oliveira Isabelle ²

¹ Department of the Farias Brito University Center (FBUNI) and Postgraduate Department of the Euvaldo Lodi Institute (IEL), Fortaleza, Ceará, Brazil.

² Postgraduates in People Management from Farias Brito University Center (FBUNI), Fortaleza, Ceará, Brazil.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 18(01), 035–039

Publication history: Received on 22 February 2023; revised on 02 April 2023; accepted on 04 April 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.18.1.0549>

Abstract

Planning the practice of management by processes is currently defended as essential for organizations and its use is suitable for the health segment. For the elaboration of this research, a qualitative approach was used based on the ideas and definitions discussed with authors who research the same theme. The elaboration procedure was developed through bibliographical research, in which a significant range of scientific sources was consulted, consisting of works such as books, articles, and reports related to the theme addressed here. The general objective of this article is to understand the current role of management and its challenges in the Brazilian hospital environment. It is clear, at the end of this research, how much more people management in the hospital environment needs to advance, especially about dealing with and leading everyone who makes up the hospital community. Cohesive, well-structured management, with well-understood objectives and mission, will provide greater chances of achieving success within the Brazilian hospital landscape.

Keywords: People Management; Hospital Community; Planning; Health

1 Introduction

Nowadays, implementing an excellent management standard based on guidelines and principles of corporate governance will provide hospital managers with positive results in minimizing risks, optimizing resources, reducing waste, balancing clinical and business management, and internal controls, thus constituting a strategic tool that provides greater competitive advantage among healthcare service organizations.

For the development of this research, a qualitative approach was employed based on ideas and definitions discussed with authors who research the same theme. The development procedure was carried out following the scientific line of bibliographic research, by which a significant range of scientific sources, such as books, articles, and reports related to the topic discussed here, was consulted.

The general objective of this article is to understand the current role of management and its challenges in the Brazilian hospital environment. The specific objectives are: to present the foundations of People Management; to discuss the importance of the People Management sector in hospitals and to talk about the challenges and creation of human resources policies in hospitals.

This article was structured into four topics. In the first topic, the introduction was presented with a highlight on the objectives of this research. In the second, the theoretical foundation was elaborated, promoting a discussion among authors who deal with the same theme researched here. In the third topic, the methodology adopted in the elaboration of this article was explained, and finally, in the fifth topic, the final considerations were discussed.

* Corresponding author: Gomes Rickardo

2 Material and methods

For this research, a qualitative approach was employed based on ideas and definitions discussed with authors who investigate the same topic.

"The qualitative approach has proven to be an important methodological tool for scientific research, as it allows for a more detailed and in-depth analysis of the phenomenon under study, enabling an understanding of the complexities and nuances of the research object [1]."

It is known that:

Bibliographic investigation is a fundamental technique for the production of scientific knowledge, as it allows for a systematic and thorough review of the main theoretical contributions on the topic in question, enabling the identification of gaps and divergences in the literature and providing support for the development of the theoretical framework of the research [2].

Among the authors who contributed the most to theoretically support this research are: Moraci and Barbosa (2013); Chiavenato (2014); Araújo, Freitas and Araújo (2021); Arruda, Carvalho and Freitas (2022).

3 Literature Review

3.1 Fundamentals of People Management

The evolutionary process of people management is extensive and has been divided into 6 phases, namely the accounting phase, legal phase, technician phase, administrative phase, strategic phase, and the phase focused on recognizing the value of human/intellectual capital, as can be observed in Figure 1. Its beginnings were formed by administrative theses, with a focus on labor legislation and Taylorist-Fordist references. Its nomenclature as people management began to emerge in the 1950s, and the sector of people management that we know today was previously known as the department responsible for verifying payments, delays, absences, and the like.

Figure 1 Evolutionary Process of People Management

Source: Sousa (2014) [3]

According to Chiavenato (2014), people management is defined as the set of policies and practices necessary to conduct managerial aspects related to people or human resources, including recruitment, selection, training, rewards, and performance evaluation. Over the years, people management has become one of the most important sectors in organizations, working directly with top management and strategic planning, and this is no different in the healthcare environment. Chiavenato (2014) also considers viewing people as partners in organizations. [4]

As such, they would provide knowledge, skills, competencies, and, above all, the most important contribution to organizations: the intelligence that provides rational decisions and gives meaning and direction to business objectives. In this sense, people constitute the human and intellectual capital of the organization.

Successful organizations treat their employees as partners in the business and providers of competencies, not just as hired employees. Knowing that organizations undergo various changes in their general context, the HR sector must perform its tasks innovatively, meeting the expectations of the company and its employees, and not just seeking results and achieving its goals. Thus, in the current scenario, the sector becomes actively involved in promoting the necessary strategies in organizations and acting as an interface between other areas [5].

According to Porto and Granetto (2020), people management is vital for the effective functioning of the hospital institution. Organization and dedication are some of the pillars for achieving health objectives, so managers must make a total commitment to promoting differential and modern actions in order to update employees to the current moment, so that the principles and objectives of the institution can be achieved [6].

3.2 Importance of the People Management Sector in Hospitals

The action of the human resource management sector in organizations that work directly with healthcare professionals is characterized by limited autonomy in terms of innovation in management practices or changes in human resource models. Structurally, the sector is linked to the general direction or administrative management of the institution in which it is located, and politically and technically, to the Human Resources Directorate (HRD) of the State Health Department.

In the private sphere, most human resource management sectors are subordinate to the administrative management or general direction of the organization. In this case, it should be noted that such organizations have a typical structure of private companies, and the human resources area has a strategic role in the organization, acting both at the decision-making level and in the implementation of sector policies [7].

It is understood that hospital administration needs to balance two fundamental points for the smooth running of the institution: human and financial resources. This is only possible with the performance of managers capable of planning, organizing, controlling, and obviously, leading their subordinate teams effectively, so that everyone makes good use of materials, inputs, and the available budget [8].

Hospitals have several segments beyond the technical area that includes all their multidisciplinary professionals (specialist doctors, nurses, nursing technicians, psychologists, among others), such as the administrative, cleaning, financial, warehouses, pharmacy areas, and each area with its own team led by a responsible manager who directs and manages the team, and they have their superiors to whom they report [9].

For this reason, personnel management in the hospital environment is even more important, and each area must perform its role correctly, always seeking humanization and quality [10].

3.3 Challenges and Human Resources Policies Creation in Hospitals

The World Health Organization's (WHO) report highlights the importance of human resources in health systems. In the Brazilian case, this importance is perceived by managers, workers, and government representatives, who acknowledge that the formation, performance, and management of human resources deeply affect the quality of services provided and the degree of user satisfaction [11]; [12].

Brazilian hospitals are subject to different administrative regimes and management models. Braga Neto, Barbosa, and Santos (2009) distinguish three major groups of hospitals based on property ownership and administrative rules of operation [9].

The first group is publicly owned and integrated into the public administration. The second is privately owned but composed differently with public interests, and the third is private, operated according to market rules, and may or may not provide services for SUS (Brazil's public health system) [12]; [13]; [14].

Entry into hospitals guided by public rules is still hindered by the lack of regular hiring processes, causing the need to hire professionals under other more immediate and flexible work relationships [11].

According to the WHO, the three main challenges in the field of people management are to improve recruitment, help the workforce improve its performance, and reduce worker turnover [11].

The construction of human resources policies raises the following issues: human resources policies represent choices about courses of action and procedures that interest public reason and certain notions of public welfare – social and economic – and good coexistence, which are related to the regulation of the distribution of the following goods:

- The set and profile of human resources offered to service users, which largely define quality, effectiveness, timeliness, as well as real access of the population to health services;
- Opportunities for work, salaries and remuneration, incentives, career opportunities, and advanced training offered by the utilization system;
- Educational opportunities and access to the professions system, both individually and collectively;
- Exclusive rights titles and reserved titles and certificates that confer legal ownership rights over fields of work and market reserves, among others [15].

When considering the issues for the construction of the Human Resources Policy and, consequently, for the distribution of those goods, we are referring to the consideration of two fundamental systems: on one hand, those issues related to the system of human resources production – training/preparation for work; on the other hand, issues related to the human resources utilization system – work management [15].

It is on these two fields of intervention and their necessary interrelationships that we must build HR policies for health: the world of education and the world of work. Conforming and intermediating the definition and implementation of the policy for these two large fields, we consider Regulatory Action and the Planning function as fundamental components of this process [15].

The HR Policy involves choices of courses of action that guide the HR Development, which consists of the design and implementation of processes of improvement or optimization of this set of elements of the systems of production and utilization of human resources, that is, the organizations and sets of institutions of these "systems" and the mechanisms and procedures operated by them [15].

4 Conclusion

It is well known that the hospital environment presents characteristics within its complexity, therefore it can be said that it is a multifaceted and diversified environment, and therefore it is necessary for the management sector to be ready to assume the responsibility of working with people, notably hospital management which brings with it a very important task for effective health care, taking into consideration that order and organization are fundamental within a hospital organization.

Research reveals that people management in the hospital environment brings with it several challenges, primarily due to being associated with the most important recognized legal good which is life. Additionally, there are other problems, notably in the public healthcare network where essential materials for daily work activities are often lacking. This situation ends up causing stress and anxiety among healthcare actors, and this is just one of the reasons why hospital managers must be prepared to handle it.

In this bibliographic study, it was possible to glimpse a little more about the role of personnel management within hospital organizations, and it was found that the task is not easy, with several challenges to face. Therefore, it is perceived that there is still a lot that needs to be done for people management in the hospital environment, especially with regard to dealing with and leading everyone who makes up the hospital community. A cohesive, well-structured management with well-understood objectives and mission will enable greater chances of success within the Brazilian hospital panorama.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank Professor M. Sc. Fernanda Moreno (Coordinator of the MBA in People Management Course) and the Farias Brito University Center (FBUNI) for all their attention.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors assure that there is no conflict of interest with the publication of the manuscript or an institution or product mentioned in the manuscript and/or important for the result of the presented study.

References

- [1] Silva, M. H. G. F. & Alves, Z. M. M. B. (2019). Qualitative analysis of interview data: a proposal. *Paidéia* (Ribeirão Preto), n. 2, p. 61-69, 1992. ISSN: 0103-863X.
- [2] Silva, M. H. G. F. (2021). *Bibliographic research: techniques and strategies for scientific research*. São Paulo: Atlas.
- [3] Sousa, F. (2014). *Contemporary Organizational Models*. Sobral: Vale do Acaraú Institute.
- [4] Chiavenato, I. (2014). *People Management: The New Role of Human Resources in Organizations*. 4th ed. Barueri: Manole.
- [5] Barbosa, A. C. Q., Costa, A. M., Garcia, M. F. R., Silva, E. M. da, Oliveira, F. P. de, & Gomes, A. P. R. (2018). Mais Médicos Program: how to evaluate the impact of an innovative approach to overcoming human resources inequalities. *Revista Panamericana de Salud Pública*, 42. ISSN: 1680-5348.
- [6] Porto, M. E. A. & Granetto, S. Z. (2020). *People Management in Hospital Environments: A Review of the Main Points of Efficient Management*. *Brazilian Journal of Development*, Curitiba, v.6, n.6, p.38366-38382, Jun. ISSN: 2525-8761. Available at: <https://www.brazilianjournals.com/index.php/BRJD/article/view/11798/9865>. Accessed on: Nov. 22, 2022.
- [7] Maia, H. B & Benevento, C.T. (2014). *People Management Applied in Health*. EFDeportes.com, Digital Magazine. Buenos Aires, Year 19, No. 196, September.
- [8] Arruda A.L., Carvalho M.R & Freitas, C.F. (2022). *People Management in the Hospital Environment*. *Scientific Journal*. v. 1 n. 1.
- [9] Araújo, V. G. C., Freitas, W. R. de S. & Araújo, E. G. (2021). *Human Resource Management in Hospitals*. *Proceedings of the South-Mato-Grossense Administration Symposium*, v. 4, n. 4, p. 430-440, Jul. 1.
- [10] Chaves, L. D. P. et al. (2015). *Governance, Hygiene, and Hospital Cleaning: Nursing Management Space*. Florianópolis. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/0104-0707201500004010014>. Accessed on: November 27, 2022.
- [11] Seixas, P. H. D. (2002). *Assumptions for the elaboration of human resources policy in national health systems*. In: Brazil, Ministry of Health. *Health Human Resources Policy: international seminar*. Brasília. p. 100-113.
- [12] Moraci, M. & Barbosa, A. (2013). *Human Resources Management in Hospitals of the Brazilian Unified Health System (SUS) and Its Relation to the Care Model: A Study in Hospitals of Belo Horizonte, Minas Gerais*. *Rev. Adm. Pública — Rio De Janeiro* 47 (1): 205-225, Jan./Feb. 2013. ISSN: 1982-3134.
- [13] Braga Neto, F. C., Barbosa, P. R. & Santos, I. S. (2009). *Hospital care: historical evolution and trends*. In: Giovanella, L. et al. (Org.). (2009). *Health policies and systems in Brazil*. Rio de Janeiro: Fiocruz Editora. p. 665-704.
- [14] Giovanella, L. et al. (Org.). (2009). *Health policies and systems in Brazil*. Rio de Janeiro: Fiocruz Editora. p. 665-704.
- [15] Brazil. Ministry of Health. (2003). *Human Resources Policy for SUS: Balance and Perspectives*. Brasília: Ministry of Health, Health Policies Secretariat, General Coordination of Human Resources Policy.